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8 **Population decline of Capercaillie (*Tetrao urogallus aquitanicus*) in central Pyrenees**

9 Running title: Population decline of Capercaillie in Pyrenees

10
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34

35

36 **Abstract**

37 Long-term monitoring of endangered birds is essential to estimate population trends and to
38 identify potential causes of population decline. This is particularly important for alpine birds
39 inhabiting mountain areas at the boundaries of their range. Here we analyse the population trend
40 of Capercaillie in the Spanish central Pyrenees based on annual surveys carried out between 2000
41 and 2017. We found a significant population decline (around 58%) in the number of birds counted
42 in leks. Most capercaillies inhabit coniferous forests of Black pine with abundant Bilberry and
43 Rhododendron understory. The number of males declined at lower altitudes and in more exposed
44 orientations, in a scenario consistent with the differential rate of loss of habitat quality due to
45 climate change. We hypothesized that one of the main causes of the Capercaillie decline could be
46 a low breeding success (average annual productivity 0.67 chicks per female). In light of the
47 decline rates observed, the Pyrenean population should be relisted as endangered in the Spanish
48 National Catalogue of Endangered Species. This consideration in a higher degree of protection
49 should guarantee the adoption of management measures to reverse or slow down the general trend
50 of decline of the species in the south of its range.

51

52 **Key words:** alpine birds, breeding success, conservation, grouse, habitat preference, monitoring
53 data, population trend, TRIM

54

55 **Resumen**

56 El seguimiento a largo plazo de las aves amenazadas es esencial para estimar las tendencias
57 poblacionales e identificar las posibles causas de declive, siendo particularmente importante en
58 el caso de las aves alpinas que habitan en áreas montañosas en los límites de su área de
59 distribución. Analizamos la tendencia poblacional del Urogallo en los Pirineos centrales

60 españoles a partir de investigaciones realizadas entre 2000 y 2017. Encontramos un declive
61 significativo de la población (alrededor del 58%) en el número de aves contados en las áreas de
62 exhibición (lek). La mayoría de los urogallos habitan bosques de coníferas de pino negro con una
63 cobertura elevada de Arándano y Rododendro en el sotobosque. El número de machos disminuyó
64 más rápidamente a altitudes más bajas y en orientaciones más expuestas, en un escenario
65 consistente con la tasa diferencial de pérdida de calidad del hábitat debido al cambio climático.
66 Nuestra hipótesis es que una de las principales causas del declive del urogallo podría ser un bajo
67 éxito de reproducción (productividad media anual de 0,67 pollos por hembra). A la luz de las
68 tasas de disminución observadas, debería cambiarse la categoría del Catálogo Español de Especies
69 Amenazadas de Vulnerable a En Peligro de Extinción. Esta consideración de un mayor grado de
70 protección legal debería garantizar la adopción de medidas de gestión para revertir o desacelerar
71 la tendencia general de declive de la especie en el sur de su área de distribución.

72

73 **Palabras clave:** aves alpinas, conservación, éxito reproductor, preferencias del hábitat,
74 tetraónidas, tendencia poblacional, TRIM

75 **Introduction**

76 European mountain birds are declining, mainly due to the high vulnerability of alpine habitats to
77 climate change and local land use practices (Flousek et al., 2015; Lehikoinen et al., 2019). The
78 Western Capercaillie *Tetrao urogallus* is a bird of conservation concern (Storch, 2007a) that is
79 experiencing a severe decline in many regions of Europe (Moss et al., 2000; Storch 2007a; Sirkiä
80 et al., 2010; Ewing et al., 2012; Zawadzki & Zawadzka 2012; Eaton et al., 2015). The decline of
81 European Capercaillie populations started in the 20th century, beginning earlier in southern areas
82 (Storch 2007a), due to poor breeding success and low recruitment rate (Obeso & Bañuelos 2003;
83 Jahren et al., 2016). The latter has been related to factors such as habitat loss, habitat
84 fragmentation, illegal hunting, climate change or increase of outdoor recreation (Moss et al., 2001;
85 Obeso & Bañuelos 2003; Quevedo et al., 2006a; Thiel et al., 2008; Morán-Luis et al., 2014).

86 Capercaillie is a polygamous grouse with an ‘exploded’ lek breeding system (i.e., communal
87 display areas used by males in the breeding season) (Wegge et al., 2013). Leks occur in forest
88 habitats (Summers et al., 2004a). The occurrence of the Capercaillie is fundamentally linked to
89 the taiga forests of the Eurasian area, although it also appears in some mountainous areas of the
90 centre (Alps, Vosges and Jura), South (Cantabrian and Pyrenean) and East (Balkans) of Europe
91 (Storch 2007a). The Spanish population of Capercaillie is distributed across two main areas: the
92 Cantabrian and the Pyrenees. Both areas represent the southwestern limit of the species' global
93 range, where they were isolated after the last quaternary glaciation that triggered their speciation
94 (Canut et al., 2011). The Cantabrian population is represented by the subspecies *T. u. cantabricus*
95 (Storch et al., 2006), while that of the Pyrenees is represented by the *T. u. aquitanicus*, a western
96 lineage shared with the Balkans (Duriez et al., 2007; Bajc et al., 2011). The distribution of the
97 Pyrenean Capercaillie population is approximately continuous in France, while in Spain it is
98 fragmented into two areas: a small western core between Navarra and western Huesca provinces
99 and a much larger one from the “Cinca valley” in Huesca to the “Alto Ter” in Catalonia (Andorra
100 included, Ménoni et al., 2004).

101 In the Pyrenees, most of the studies on the population trend of the Capercaillie have been based
102 on the comparison of the magnitude of change between surveys every 5-10 years (Ménoni et al.,

103 2004; Ballesteros et al., 2006). The first surveys of the Capercaillie population of the Spanish
104 Pyrenees were conducted in early 1980's. Subsequently, in 2005 a new estimate of the number of
105 active leks was made, including a count of the number of males (Ballesteros et al., 2006).
106 Although a decline close to 40% in the number of males between both surveys was observed,
107 most leks remained active. Nevertheless, both the differences in the area surveyed between the
108 two censuses (i.e., the number of known and visited leks) and the absence of an interannual
109 monitoring protocol, make it difficult to assess the degree of decline of the population in the
110 Spanish Pyrenees.

111 The subspecies *aquitanicus* is catalogued as "Vulnerable" in Spain under the National Catalogue
112 of Endangered Species. Since 2005, Aragón region must implement a "Pyrenean Capercaillie
113 Habitat Conservation Plan" which establishes measures to guarantee long-term viability of its
114 populations. The development of this plan requires studies on the population trend and
115 reproductive success in this region of the Pyrenees (Lorente et al., 2004; Gil & Alcántara 2011).
116 In this study, we analyse population trend of the species in the Spanish central Pyrenees (Aragón)
117 based on an interannual monitoring carried out during 18 years. The aims of our study are to (1)
118 estimate the population trend of males and females in leks; (2) characterize breeding habitats; (3)
119 assess how different types of habitat can affect decline rates; (4) identify the relationship between
120 productivity and population decline.

121

122 **Methods**

123 *Study area*

124 Our study was carried out in the central Spanish Pyrenees (Huesca province, Aragón), specifically
125 in the regions of Jacetania (Veral, Aragón Subordán and Aragón valleys), Sobrarbe (Cinca and
126 Cinqueta valleys) and Ribagorza (Esera and Noguera- Ribagorzana valleys). These areas are
127 identified in the Pyrenean Capercaillie Habitat Conservation Plan in Aragón (Decree 300/2015).
128 The plan identifies 25 Critical Areas (total = 24,476 ha) that are defined as the vital areas for the
129 survival and conservation of the species (Fig. 1).

130 In central Pyrenees, Capercaillie inhabits mature coniferous forests of montane and subalpine
131 areas, with preference for Black pine *Pinus uncinata*, although it is also present in other forests
132 such as Scots pine *Pinus sylvestris* or Silver fir *Abies alba*, and occasionally in reforestation of
133 European larch *Larix europaea* and Spruce *Picea abies* (Lorente et al., 2004; Guzman &
134 Navascues 2006). From 2000 to 2017 we surveyed Capercaillie habitats during the courtship
135 period (late April – early June). Our surveys included direct and indirect bird observations,
136 including lekking sites and indirect evidence of bird presence (e.g. scat). From an initial list of
137 places with presence of the species, these surveys allowed us to increase considerably the number
138 of known leks.

139

140 *Habitat characterization and area of occupation*

141 To characterize habitat around leks, we categorically classified forests according to the dominant
142 tree and shrub species with the greatest undergrowth coverage. For each lek site, the contiguous
143 area of suitable forest with presence of Capercaillies was mapped to obtain the extent of
144 occurrence. We also documented indirect evidences of the species, such as tracks, feathers, or
145 faecal droppings (Moss et al., 2014).

146

147 *Lek counts*

148 Males and females were counted annually (2000-2017) at all leks on single visits from late April
149 to early June (Catusse & Novoa 1983). The lek location was based on historical information and
150 surveys conducted in previous years. We counted the number of males singing at each lek at
151 sunrise (Catusse & Novoa 1983). To determine the exact location of every lek, each season we
152 visited the sites the afternoon before the count, and, following male vocalisations, we located the
153 roosting tree that birds use during the night close to the display territory (Wegge et al., 2013).
154 During visits, we also counted the number of females that attended the lek. The number of females
155 counted in the leks may not reflect their actual abundance because they may visit more than one
156 lek during the lekking season and they show up only for short periods (Storch 1997). Nevertheless,

157 long-term series of female counts might provide valuable information to estimate population
158 trends.

159

160 *Breeding success*

161 Transects (Rajala 1974; Leclercq 1987; Canut et al., 1996) and trained dogs were used to estimate
162 breeding success (Ellison 1979; Ménoni 1987; Wegge & Kastdalen 2008), in order to flush and
163 count females and any associated chicks. Breeding surveys were carried out from 2002 to 2007
164 during late July and early August, coinciding with the chick-rearing period (Gil & Alcántara
165 2011). We only surveyed areas of suitable habitat where the presence of Capercaillie in the spring
166 or in previous summers was confirmed. In order to avoid double counts, transects were started at
167 lower altitudes than the sites used by capercaillies. Transects were carried out by a team of
168 between five and eight people that walked line abreast separated from each other by 15-20 meters.
169 Transects with trained dogs were carried out by two people. Surveys were conducted covering
170 the entire forest area with suitable habitat for Capercaillie at a slow speed, maintaining the
171 altitudinal elevation and visual contact between the observers. Each plot was surveyed for three
172 to four hours early in the morning.

173 Productivity was measured as the mean number of chicks per female (including those with no
174 chicks). We analysed the relationship between productivity and Capercaillie abundance measured
175 as number of full-grown birds. Following Summers et al. (2010), changes in numbers in density
176 (i.e., number of full-grown males and females per 100 ha) along transects were expressed as a
177 percentage change from one summer (year t) to the next (year $t + 1$), and compared with
178 productivity in the previous summer (year t) in a linear regression analysis. Even though male
179 Capercaillies do not breed until the age of three or more (Wegge & Larsen 1987; Storch 1997,
180 2001), we assumed that one and two-year-old males could also be part of the count at leks and
181 summer counts (Wegge & Larsen 1987).

182

183 *Trend analysis*

184 We evaluated Capercaillie population trend using the software TRIM (*Trend & Indices for*
185 *Monitoring data*, TRIM 3.54). TRIM is statistical software developed for the analysis of long-
186 term time series data from animal monitoring programmes (Pannekoek & Van Strien 2005). In
187 recent years, TRIM has become one of the most used software for bird population trend
188 assessment (Gregory et al., 2009; Gregory & Van Strien 2010; Flousek et al., 2015; Lehikoinen
189 et al., 2019). TRIM estimates annual population change indices implementing log-linear
190 regression models with Poisson error terms that represent the effect of change between years. The
191 TRIM index value at the first time point (or another point considered as baseline year) is 1.0 and
192 it is taken as reference for trends in subsequent years. The main advantages of TRIM are: (1) the
193 correction for both overdispersion and serial correlation; (2) incorporation of significant change
194 points in trends; (3) analyses of time series counts with missing observations (Pannekoek & Van
195 Strien 2005; Gregory & Van Strien, 2010). The latter is particularly advantageous when time
196 series are incomplete due to lack of sampling, situation that occurred in some of our study areas.
197 To overcome this limitation, missing counts for specific sites and years were estimated by TRIM
198 from changes in all other sites (Gregory et al., 2005). We calculated population trend from 2000
199 to 2017 using a TRIM linear trend model and we used 2000 as base year. The goodness-of-fit of
200 models was tested by Pearson's Chi-squared statistic and by the Likelihood Ratio test. We started
201 the analysis with a model with change points at each year, and used the stepwise selection
202 procedure to identify change points with significant changes in slope (based on Wald tests and a
203 significance-level threshold value of 0.05; Pannekoek & van Strien 2005). In order to avoid
204 underestimation of standard errors, we took into account overdispersion and serial correlation in
205 TRIM's options for all models. We used three categorical variables: (1) Habitat type (i.e., Scots
206 pine or Black pine forests); (2) Orientation (Northern vs. other orientations), and (3) Elevation
207 (above or below the median altitude of leks; i.e., 1900 m). Wald tests (provided by TRIM) were
208 used to assess the significance of change points and to test for differences in trends between
209 covariate categories. A set of 16 models was generated: eight for each sex group, including the
210 combination of categorical variables (i.e., habitat, altitude, orientation) and a model without
211 covariates. We selected the most parsimonious model using the Akaike information criterion

212 corrected for small samples (AIC_c), and we rescaled model values using the minimum AIC_c to
213 provide evidence of the relative support for each model: $\Delta AIC_c = AIC_c - AIC_{c \text{ min}}$. We consider
214 that models with a $\Delta AIC_c < 2$ have strong support, and those with $\Delta AIC_c > 10$ have less support
215 (Burnham and Anderson 1998). According to Pannekoek & van Strien (2005), trends were
216 classified taken into account the slope imputed (i.e., multiplicative value) and the standard error
217 provided by TRIM in the following six categories: Steep decline, Moderate decline, Stable,
218 Moderate increase, Strong increase, and Uncertain.

219

220 **Results**

221 We monitored 39 different leks attended by at least one male during the breeding season. These
222 leks were visited from 4 to 18 years between 2000 and 2017 (mean 8.92 ± 3.88 visits/lek during
223 the 18 years of the study period). Overall, the sampling effort was of 348 count stations, with an
224 average of 19.33 ± 7.63 leks visited per year. A total of 34 transects were carried out in 11 different
225 localities during the period 2002-2007. The total area surveyed annually ranged between 349 and
226 501 ha.

227

228 *Habitat characterization*

229 Leks were mainly located in continuous Black pine forests (79.5%). We located some leks in
230 mixed Black pine and Silver fir forest (5.1%). The remaining leks were located in Scots pine
231 forests, often mixed with Black pine, Silver fir or Common beech (*Fagus sylvatica*). Five species
232 of shrubs were identified as the main structural species of the understory (Supplementary material
233 appendix 1, Figure A1). At 84.6% of the leks, the understory was characterized by a mixture of
234 Bilberry *Vaccinium myrtillus* and Rhododendron *Rhododendron ferrugineum* (Supplementary
235 material appendix 1, Figure A2). Leks were located at altitudes between 1550 and 2180 m a.s.l.
236 (median = 1900 m) (Supplementary material appendix 1, Figure A3). Northern orientations (N,
237 NW, NE) were more frequent (71.8% of leks) than southern, eastern or western orientations.

238 The extent of occurrence of the Capercaillie in Huesca was 2,621 ha (Fig. 1). This area is divided
239 into 37 fragments, nearly all of them (94.9%) including only one lek and two including two leks

240 (5.1%). The average area of these fragments was 70.8 ± 37.2 ha ($N = 37$). There was no
241 relationship between the size of these fragments and the average number of displaying males
242 (Spearman correlation, $r = 0.2370$, $N = 37$, $P = 0.158$). Nevertheless, the maximum number of
243 displaying males recorded in the study correlated with fragment size (Spearman correlation, $r =$
244 0.3879 , $N = 37$, $P = 0.018$; Fig. 2).

245

246 *Lek trend and summer counts*

247 Leks were attended by an average of 1.71 ± 0.91 males and 1.37 ± 0.40 females (only leks with
248 positive count for each sex were considered), with a maximum of seven males and six females
249 per lek. The annual percentage of visited leks with bird presence showed a significant negative
250 trend during the study period for both males ($R^2 = 0.9105$, $N = 18$, $P < 0.0001$) and females (R^2
251 $= 0.3432$, $N = 18$, $P = 0.006$). At the end of the study period (2017) more than half of the leks
252 (54.1%) had been deserted by males ($R^2 = 0.9121$, $N = 18$, $P < 0.0001$) (Fig. 3). A total of 17
253 males and 37 females were counted in the summer transects. The average density of capercaillies
254 was 2.89 ± 3.10 adults/100 ha (males: 0.68 ± 1.13 , females: 2.21 ± 2.57 , $N = 34$).

255 The number of capercaillies in leks and the density of birds estimated in summer transects around
256 these leks in the same year did not show a significant relationship (Spearman correlations, males,
257 $r = 0.3441$, $N = 21$, $P = 0.127$; females, $r = 0.2910$, $N = 18$, $P = 0.241$).

258

259 *Productivity*

260 Of the females we counted in summer transects, 45.95% ($n = 37$) were accompanied by chicks
261 (mean = 2.05 chicks/female). Considering the total number of females counted in transects, the
262 average productivity was 0.95 ± 1.31 chicks per female ($N = 37$). Mean annual productivity from
263 2002 to 2007 was 0.67 ± 0.79 chicks per female (range = 0 - 2.13; $N = 6$).

264 There was positive but non-significant correlation between the percentage change in the number
265 of males at leks and the productivity in the previous summer ($t = 0.8366$, $N = 10$, $P = 0.427$;
266 Supplementary material appendix 1, Figure A4). This relationship was negative but non-

267 significant for the indices of abundance for Capercaillie between summer counts ($t = -0.6765$, N
268 $= 19$, $P = 0.508$; Supplementary material appendix 1, Figure A4).

269

270 *Population trend*

271 For both sexes, the top ranked models classified the trend as a moderate decline (Table 1). The
272 top-ranked model for males showed higher decline (annual change = -6.18%) than females
273 (annual change = -2.76%). Despite these differences in decline rates, both sexes showed a similar
274 percentage of population decline in 2017 compared to the beginning of the study period (2000 –
275 2017), with a population reduction greater than 57% in both cases (males, 57.84%; females
276 57.61%) (Fig. 4).

277 The best model for males included the effect of altitude (Wald = 11.70, $df = 4$, $P = 0.020$). A
278 second model with similar explanatory value ($\Delta AIC_c < 2$) included the site's orientation instead,
279 although this variable had a non-significant effect. Our modelling results for females produced
280 three best models with similar support: the model without covariates and two models with altitude
281 and habitat, respectively. In the latter two models, although covariates were included, their effect
282 was not significant (altitude, Wald = 8.92, $df = 5$, $P = 0.112$; habitat, Wald = 12.58, $df = 7$, $P =$
283 0.083). There were three years with significant points of change for males (2007, Wald = 21.33,
284 $df = 2$, $P < 0.0001$; 2009, Wald = 7.57, $df = 2$, $P = 0.028$; 2016, Wald = 10.45, $df = 2$, $P = 0.005$)
285 and two for females (2000, Wald = 3.86, $df = 1$, $P = 0.0495$; 2010, Wald = 4.83, $df = 1$, $P = 0.028$;
286 2011, Wald = 4.31, $df = 1$, $P = 0.038$). For the most parsimonious models for males the estimated
287 decline was higher for populations located below 1900 m, especially in the 2010 – 2016 period,
288 and for more exposed orientations (Fig. 4).

289

290 **Discussion**

291 Long-term monitoring of endangered birds is essential to estimate population trends and to
292 identify potential causes of population decline. This is particularly important for alpine birds
293 inhabiting mountainous areas at the edge of their range (Lehikoinen et al., 2019). In this regard,
294 here we provide updated information on the distribution of the endangered Capercaillie in the

295 Pyrenees, where only 28 leks had been previously surveyed in Central Pyrenees (Aragon region)
296 (Ballesteros et al., 2006).

297 We found that both the average number of males and females attending leks was low, compared
298 with other sectors of the Pyrenees (Ménoni 1994; Canut et al., 2006) as well as populations of
299 Northern Europe (Angelstam 2004; Zawadzki & Zawadzka, 2012). Similarly, the density of birds
300 in the summer counts was lower than in other in other portions of their ranges (Moss & Oswald
301 1985; Miettinen et al., 2008) and even within the Pyrenees (Fernández-Olalla et al., 2012).

302 Studies in Northern and Central Europe have shown that male Capercaillies establish their home
303 ranges around leks in spring (Wegge & Larsen 1987; Rolstad et al., 1988; Storch 1997; Eliassen
304 & Wegge 2007), and that territory size is inversely related to the proportion of optimum habitat
305 within them (Wegge & Rolstad 1986). Likewise, the number of male birds that attend leks
306 depends on the quality and quantity of the surrounding forest habitats (Picozzi et al., 1992; Storch
307 1995a; Angelstam 2004; Summers et al., 2004a). Indeed, we found that the maximum number of
308 males recorded in leks increased with the area of favourable habitat around them. Based on these
309 evidences, it has been suggested that territorial spacing behaviour might limit the number of males
310 at leks (Wegge & Rolstad 1986). Nevertheless, this limitation in the number of males as a result
311 of the spacing pattern could result from habitat fragmentation or habitat alteration by human
312 activities, since in pristine forests leks can be attended by a greater number of males coming from
313 more distant territories (Rolstad & Wegge 1987; Wegge et al., 2003; Rolstad et al., 2009). In the
314 case of Central Pyrenees, habitat fragmentation is mainly due to human activities (Canut et al.,
315 2011), so that the number of males that can attend leks is generally limited by the availability of
316 suitable habitat, which is, in turn, constrained by climatic limitations.

317

318 *Trend*

319 Since 2000, the number lekking Capercaillie has been monitored annually at 39 sites. Our estimate
320 of male population was 89 ± 9 birds in Aragon in 2000 (Supplementary material appendix 1,
321 Figure A5).

322 This Central Spanish Pyrenean population decreased to only 37 ± 6 males at the end of the study
323 period (2017). Although the number of females counted in the leks may not reflect their actual
324 abundance (Storch 1997), our models estimate that the initial population (2000) of females that
325 visited leks was 45 ± 9 individuals and only 19 ± 4 at the end of the study period.

326 Our results show a significant population decline of Capercaillie in the Central Pyrenees during
327 the period 2000 – 2017, with a decline of more than 57% on the number of birds counted in leks.
328 This negative trend recorded in central Pyrenees is consistent with the general decline of
329 Capercaillie populations all over Europe (Moss et al., 2000; Storch 2007b; Sirkiä et al., 2010;
330 Zawadzki & Zawadzka 2012; Morán-Luis et al., 2014; Eaton et al., 2015).

331 We observed that females declined more quickly than males in the first years of study, although
332 the percentage of change is similar to the end of the period (Fig. 5). Nevertheless, the annual
333 decline rate was higher in males (-6.18% per year) than females (-2.76%). Moss et al. (2000)
334 observed a different pattern in Scotland, with a higher reduction observed in females. Even though
335 the sex ratio in chicks is higher for females (Wegge 1980; Moss & Oswald 1985; Hornfeldt et al.,
336 2001), they suggest as probable explanation that adult cocks lived longer.

337 The Cantabrian Capercaillie population has declined by 70% in the number of males at leks
338 between 1981 and 2003 (Pollo et al., 2005; Storch et al., 2006). This steep decline caused its
339 recent relisting (2018) as “critically endangered” in Spain under the National Catalogue of
340 Endangered Species. To date, the population of the Pyrenees subspecies had been interpreted to
341 be decreasing, but with a more discrete rate of decline. For instance, Ménoni et al. (2004)
342 estimated only a 5.5% decline of range in the Pyrenees between 1975 and 2000. Similarly,
343 Ballesteros et al. (2006) estimated that still 91.7% of historical leks were occupied in 2005.
344 Nonetheless, the rate of decline is different when considering the number of birds attending leks.
345 44% of the leks of the Pyrenean mountain range showed a decline in the number of males between
346 1990 and 2002, with a maximum reduction in the case of the French central Pyrenees (62% of
347 declining leks; Ménoni et al., 2004). This decline was estimated as close to 40% in the case of the
348 Spanish Pyrenees, a rate obtained from the comparison of 1983 and 2005 surveys (Ballesteros et
349 al., 2006). A more accurate estimate of the population trend, based on the interannual monitoring

350 of adult Capercaillie density for the period 1988 – 2010, found a 4% annual decrease of adult
351 birds in the Catalanian Pyrenees (Fernandez-Olalla et al., 2012).

352 Importantly, most decline rates for the Pyrenees refer to periods up to the beginning of the 2000s.
353 Therefore, the decline occurred in central Pyrenees should be significantly higher than that
354 observed in this study, since the reduction of 57% between 2000 and 2017 must be added to the
355 40% registered between 1983 and early 2000s. The subspecies *aquitanicus* is listed as
356 "Vulnerable" in Spain under the National Catalogue of Endangered Species. In light of the decline
357 rates observed since the 1980s, which seems to have intensified in recent years, the national threat
358 category of the species should be reviewed, since the criteria for a higher level of protection are
359 likely to be met.

360

361 *Breeding success*

362 One of the causes that have been most frequently invoked as a cause of the decline of Capercaillie
363 is low breeding success (Moss et al., 2000; Obeso & Bañuelos 2003; Baines et al., 2004; Summers
364 et al., 2004b; Jähren et al., 2016). Our results show a low productivity for the study period (0.95
365 ± 1.31 chicks per female). Although a short time series is available, it is noteworthy that in two
366 of the five years of monitoring the productivity was zero chicks per female (mean annual
367 productivity = 0.67 chicks per female). Despite limited sample size, this low productivity is
368 similar to that of other declining populations, such as in Scotland (Summers et al., 2004b), and is
369 within the general context of declining productivity of the species in European populations
370 (reviewed by Jähren et al., 2016). Focusing on Spanish Pyrenees, the low success has been
371 documented since the late 1980s, and the productivity has been reduced from 1.3 to less than 0.5
372 chicks per female between 1988 and 2001 (Ménoni et al., 2004). Moreover, our reproductive
373 success is slightly higher than that documented in the Catalan Pyrenees, where the productivity
374 was 0.82 chicks per female in the period 1993 – 2013 (Pimenta et al., 2014).
375 Similar to Moss & Oswald (1985) results for a Scottish population of Capercaillie, neither the
376 summer counts nor the number of males at leks were related to productivity in the previous year.

377 Nonetheless, this relationship could be subject to a high interpopulation variability, since in a
378 nearby Scottish place these variables were correlated (Summers et al., 2010).

379 Some authors have suggested that global warming could reduce Capercaillie breeding success
380 (Moss et al., 2001; Selås et al., 2011; Jahren et al., 2016), and seems to have been a major cause
381 of decline of regional Capercaillie populations (Moss et al., 2001). Nevertheless, the mechanisms
382 of this relationship are not yet understood (Jahren et al., 2016). Contrary to this prediction, in less
383 temperate regions the effect may be the opposite. For instance, Wegge & Rolstad (2017) claim
384 that in Finland boreal forest breeding success was enhanced in warmer springs. Nevertheless, it
385 has been suggested that the most southern populations and those of Atlantic climates are the most
386 vulnerable to climate change (Storch, 2007). Indeed, models based on climate scenarios for the
387 21st century forecast a reduction ranging between 99% and 100% in the potential distribution of
388 the species in Spain for the period 2041-2070 (Araújo et al., 2011).

389 In addition, predation is the most important cause of natural mortality for the Capercaillie,
390 especially in pre-adult stages (Tornberg 2001; Reif et al., 2004; Wegge & Kastdalen 2007), so
391 that is one of the main factors that reduce productivity (Marcström et al., 1988).

392

393 *Habitat*

394 In Spanish Central Pyrenees, we found that the most Capercaillies inhabit coniferous forests of
395 Black pine with abundant Bilberry and Rhododendron understory. This preference for boreal and
396 montane coniferous forests with abundant Bilberry is consistent with Capercaillie's habitat
397 selection in most European populations (Storch 1993, 2001; Wegge & Kastdalen 2008). For the
398 Pyrenean mountain range, it indicates that the species uses a considerable variability of forest
399 habitats (Monzón 1981; Ballesteros et al., 2006; Ménoni 2011), although in the southern
400 mountains it is usually associated with forests of Black pine (Ménoni 1994; Ménoni et al., 2004;
401 Pascual-Horta & Saura 2008). The results of our models indicated that the number of males
402 declined faster at lower altitudes and more exposed orientations (i.e., south, east and west). This
403 asymmetrical population decline is of conservation concern under the expected scenario of
404 climate change, so as to marginal habitats are deserted first by the loss of their quality as breeding

405 areas. In addition, this decline increased towards the end of the study period, which might be
406 interpreted as an acceleration of the consequences of climate change.

407 Bilberry is a key plant for Capercaillie diet in the Eurosiberian region (Moss et al., 1979; Storch
408 1995b; Quevedo et al., 2006b; Blanco-Fontao et al., 2010), so that Bilberry management is the
409 cornerstone of the Capercaillie conservation. The Capercaillie is strongly linked with Bilberry
410 distribution in the Pyrenees (Ménoni 2011; Montané et al., 2016). Campión et al. (2011) claim
411 that in some areas in the southern Pyrenees, Bilberry can be replaced in the diet by Bearberry. We
412 found that in 23.1% of the places with the presence of Capercaillie the Bearberry was present, but
413 only in three places (7.7%) was the Bilberry absent. Bearing in mind that two of these places have
414 recently lost their lek, it is clear that this habitat is used marginally by the Capercaillie in the
415 Central Pyrenees.

416

417 *Habitat management*

418 Habitat management is crucial for the conservation of the European populations of Capercaillie
419 (Suchant & Braunisch 2004; Hancock et al., 2011; Broome et al., 2014). Baines et al. (2004)
420 suggest that there is a minimum of 15–20% Bilberry ground cover so as habitat may be suitable
421 for Capercaillie. In the Pyrenees, it has been estimated that the optimal coverage of Bilberry for
422 Capercaillie should be between 50-80% (Campión et al., 2011). Based on studies conducted in
423 these mountains, Montané et al. (2016) stated that canopy cover and understory composition
424 (particularly the Rhododendron cover) determine the cover and fruit production of Bilberry. They
425 concluded that reducing Rhododendron cover has a strong positive effect on Bilberry cover and
426 fruit production. Nevertheless, Rhododendron clear-cutting experiences conducted in the region,
427 apparently, have not influenced Capercaillie density and clear-cuts have been more beneficial for
428 wild ungulates and livestock (Camprodon et al., 2016). Other authors suggest that the elimination
429 of undergrowth could have negative consequences, such as the increase of predation rates, mainly
430 on chicks (Wegge et al., 2005; Kvasnes & Storaas 2007). Despite these controversial results, it
431 has been suggested that the species needs a certain level of spatial heterogeneity (Canut et al.,
432 2011). For instance, Mikoláš et al. (2017) showed that, in primary forests of the Carpathian

433 Mountains, a mixed-severity disturbance regime is required to generate diverse habitats suitable
434 for Capercaillie, and conclude that natural disturbance should be mimicked as a conservation tool
435 in protected areas.

436 Previous studies have shown that predator control may increase Capercaillie productivity
437 (Marcström et al., 1988; Kauhala et al., 2000; Baines et al., 2004; Summers et al., 2004b). For
438 instance, Moreno-Opo et al. (2015) showed that breeding success of a Pyrenean population of
439 Capercaillie was enhanced in areas where carnivores were removed. Nevertheless, some authors
440 have questioned the effectiveness of predator control and have highlighted the occurrence of
441 undesired side-effects (Rushton et al., 2006; Woodroffe & Redpat 2005). These limitations are
442 added to the negative view that society has on predator control, so that alternative management
443 strategies must be promoted (Moreno-Opo et al., 2015). Generalist mesopredators can reach high
444 densities in the absence of top-down control (Kämmerle et al., 2017), so that one of the proposed
445 alternatives to predator control is the recovery of apex predators (Ripple et al., 2014; Moreno-
446 Opo et al., 2015). For instance, the recovery of Eurasian lynx (*Lynx lynx*) in Finland coincided
447 with a decrease in red fox density and the recovery of the hare, one of its main prey (Elmhagen et
448 al., 2010). Precisely, the Eurasian lynx was present in the Pyrenees until the early-nineteenth
449 century (Clavero & Delibes, 2013) and according to some sources until the early twentieth century
450 (Jiménez et al., 2018). Therefore, its reintroduction in the Pyrenees might have a positive effect
451 on Capercaillie breeding success through a reduction in potential predators.

452 The impact of predators may contribute to the local extinction of Capercaillie populations when
453 they act on populations affected by lack of both suitable habitat and connectivity (Wegge et al.,
454 1992; Kämmerle et al., 2017). Furthermore, this negative effect of predation could be
455 compensated under optimal habitat conditions, so conservation actions should be aimed at
456 improving both habitat connectivity and quality (Sirkiä et al., 2012). It has been suggested that
457 increased woodland size and reduction of fragmentation might decrease the presence of some
458 predators associated with the interface between open habitats and woodland (Wegge et al., 1992;
459 Summers et al., 2004b). These measures could be effective against corvids, which have been

460 documented as predators of Capercaillie nests (Storch 2001; Baines et al., 2004; Summers et al.,
461 2004b).

462 Finally, in addition to the abovementioned factors (i.e., habitat loss, predation, climate change),
463 human disturbance could be contributing to Capercaillie decline (Storch 2013). Human presence
464 alters Capercaillie's behaviour by increasing stress levels (Summers et al., 2007; Thiel et al.,
465 2007; Jenni-Eiermann & Arlettaz 2008; Thiel et al., 2008). Outdoor recreation has a negative
466 impact on Capercaillie habitat selection (Suárez-Seoane & García-Rovés 2004; Moss et al., 2014).
467 It has been shown that some recreational infrastructures (e.g., hiking, cross-country trails and ski
468 trails) cause habitat reduction in winter (Canut et al., 2004; Jenni-Eiermann & Arlettaz 2008;
469 Canut et al., 2011; Coppes et al., 2017). In the same way, birds avoid infrastructures such as
470 mountain bike trails in summer (Coppes et al., 2017). We have documented the decline in the
471 number of birds in some leks where human disturbance has increased in recent years, especially
472 winter activities such as cross-country skiing and snowshoeing. The control of outdoor recreation
473 in Capercaillie habitats is probably one of the main challenges that managers should take into
474 account to improve the conservation status of the species.

475 In summary, considering the high rates of decline observed in the Central Pyrenees, and those
476 documented in other sectors of the mountain range, we suggest reconsidering the protection status
477 of the subspecies in regional and national legislation. Therefore, Pyrenean populations of
478 Capercaillie should be relisted as endangered under the Spanish National Catalogue of
479 Endangered Species. This consideration in a higher degree of protection should guarantee the
480 adoption of management measures to reverse or slow down the general trend of decline of the
481 species in the south of its range.

482

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489

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788 current volume on www.ardeola.org

789 **Figure captions**

790 **Fig. 1** Study area in the Spanish Central Pyrenees.

791 **Fig. 2** Correlation between the maximum number of displaying Capercaillie males in leks
792 and area of fragments with presence of the species around each lek (period 2000 – 2017,
793 Aragon, Central Spanish Pyrenees).

794 **Fig. 3** Percentage of active leks for males (grey line), females (black line) and
795 accumulated percentage of deserted leks (dotted line) over time in Aragon (Central
796 Spanish Pyrenees).

797 **Fig. 4** TRIM imputed index according to the two top-ranked models for males over time.
798 The top-ranked model included altitude (upper figure) and the second one included
799 orientation (lower figure).

800 **Fig. 5** TRIM imputed index of the Capercaillie breeding population in Central Spanish
801 Pyrenees from 2000 to 2017. Trend of males and females are shown separately based on
802 a linear model without covariates. Errors bars indicate standard error.

803 **Table 1.** Summary of TRIM model results for the period 2000 – 2017. The results of all
804 models are shown for each sex group. Abbreviations: OD, overdispersion. SC, serial
805 correlation. LR, Likelihood Ratio. AIC_c, Akaike information criterion corrected for small
806 samples. AIC_w, Akaike weight. OMS, Overall Multiplicative Slope imputed. SE,
807 Standard error. * P < 0.05; ** P < 0.01

Model	OD	SC	LR	AIC _c	ΔAIC _c	AIC _w	OMS ± SE	Trend class
Males								
Altitude	0.59	0.283	203.33	-400.56	0.00	0.47	0.9382±0.0082	Moderate decline **
Orientation	0.59	0.258	205.09	-398.80	1.76	0.19	0.9385±0.0081	Moderate decline **
Orientation + Altitude	0.597	0.286	203.79	-397.88	2.69	0.14	0.9382±0.0083	Moderate decline **
No covariates	0.583	0.273	211.82	-398.18	2.38	0.13	0.9312±0.0088	Steep decline *
Habitat	0.597	0.281	208.47	-395.42	5.14	0.04	0.9362±0.0083	Moderate decline **
Habitat + Altitude	0.586	0.269	201.18	-394.49	6.08	0.03	0.9362±0.0082	Moderate decline **
Habitat + Orientation	0.589	0.268	203.38	-392.29	8.28	0.01	0.9365±0.0083	Moderate decline **
Habitat + Orientation + Altitude	0.588	0.268	199.7	-387.61	12.95	0.00	0.9360±0.0082	Moderate decline **
Females								
No covariates	0.930	0.021	277.86	-274.14	0.00	0.42	0.9724±0.0134	Moderate decline *
Altitude	0.933	0.016	274.86	-273.03	1.11	0.26	0.9646±0.0118	Moderate decline **
Habitat	0.897	-0.036	267.17	-272.72	1.42	0.22	0.9673±0.0125	Moderate decline **
Habitat + Altitude	0.907	-0.006	267.42	-270.25	3.89	0.07	0.9650±0.0116	Moderate decline **
Orientation	0.939	0.010	279.78	-268.11	6.03	0.02	0.9679±0.0130	Moderate decline *
Habitat + Orientation	0.909	-0.020	260.86	-264.81	9.33	0.00	0.9651±0.0133	Moderate decline **
Orientation + Altitude	0.948	0.006	274.77	-262.90	11.24	0.00	0.9692±0.0138	Moderate decline **
Habitat + Orientation + Altitude	0.925	-0.035	255.16	-256.15	17.99	0.00	0.9647±0.0136	Moderate decline **

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Figure 1

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Figure 2

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Figure 5